

Studies in Physico-Chemical Properties of Caseins. Part XII. Hysteresis Effect in the Sorption-Desorption Isotherms of Polar Vapour Adsorbates on Casein and its Major Fractions.

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Sorption-desorption isotherms of water, methanol and ethanol on casein and its α - and β -fractions show appreciable hysteresis which, however, does not persist all along the isotherm. The size of the hysteresis loop, in the case of water, keeps on decreasing appreciably at each successive cycle while that in the case of methanol decreases only slightly and that in the case of ethanol remains almost unchanged. The hysteresis effect increases with increase in molecular size of the adsorbate, the area of the loop decreasing in the order: ethanol > methanol > water. The extent of sorption and degree of swelling, however, decrease in the reverse order. The data have been examined in the light of the current theories of hysteresis. The slow rate of diffusion of adsorbate molecules from the micropores of casein appears to be an important factor to be taken into account. The denaturation of casein results in lowering the extent of sorption and area of the hysteresis loop, due probably to partial loss of surface and collapse of micropores.

ADSORPTION isotherms of water¹, methanol, ethanol and *n*-butanol² by casein and its major fractions were reported in previous publications. The monolayer capacity as obtained by B.E.T. and Harkins and Jura equations as well as from the knee of the isotherm were in fairly good agreement and the thermodynamic functions such as differential free energy, enthalpy and entropy of the process were found to diminish abruptly on the completion of the monolayer in the case of each adsorbent. The *t*-plots³ of the various adsorbates indicated the presence of micropores of width varying between 11.7 and 14.8 Å in casein and its fractions². Several investigators have reported hysteresis in the sorption-desorption isotherms of polar vapours in the native as well as denatured state. Seehof⁴ working with casein reported the area of the hysteresis loop to vary with the arginine, histidine and lysine groups of the adsorbent and the hydrogen-bonding capacity of the adsorbate. Benson and Richardson⁵ working with egg albumin, bovine plasma albumin and gelatin, in the native as well as denatured state, found the hysteresis to be reproducible even after a series of four or five cycles. Rao et al working with dhal⁶, egg albumin, casein, and gelatin, etc⁷, and using water as the adsorbate, found the size of the loops to diminish at each subsequent cycle and to disappear after 4 or 5 cycles. Berlin, Anderson and Pallansch⁸ found the residual moisture held by a water-dried casein to be bound so firmly that it could not be desorbed even on pumping at 10^{-6} torr at the ambient temperature for a period of 8 days. This observation puts the concept of a water-dried protein to some doubt. Attempts have also been made⁵ to correlate the area of the hysteresis loop with the extent of sorption and molecular volume of the adsorbate, though not with much success. It was thought of interest to study sorption-desorption isotherms of water, methanol and ethanol vapours, each one of which is polar and is capable of forming hydrogen bonds, on bovine casein

and its α - and β -fractions in order to get some further insight into the mechanism of hysteresis involved in such systems.

Experimental

Casein was isolated from bovine skim milk and fractionated into α - and β -caseins by following the procedure described earlier¹. These were dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid to constant weight which took nearly 2 days. Portions of the caseins were denatured by boiling in water for 2 hr followed by washing first with acetone and then with ether. These were also dried in vacuum as mentioned above. The dried material, in each case, was ground and passed through a 200-mesh sieve. Methanol (A. R., B. D. H.) was redistilled over sodium while ethanol was recovered from rectified spirit by the usual distillation over lime and sodium. The isotherms were determined at 35° ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) by the McBain balance technique using quartz fibre spring of 18.5 cm/g sensitivity. The various systems were found to approach equilibrium within 2-3 hr during the sorption process and 3-7 hr during the desorption process. The results of various replicates agreed within 0.6% of one another.

For swelling studies, casein (~1 g) tablets (circular) of diameter and thickness equal to ~ 1.8 cm and ~ 0.3 cm respectively were placed in a given liquid in a petric dish. The changes in dimensions were determined after 3 hours during which time maximum swelling had occurred. The increase in volume was calculated from the data.

Results and Discussion

Adsorption isotherms of water on casein and its major fractions for the first, second and fourth cycles are the plotted in Fig. 1, 2 and 3, respectively. These

Fig. 1 - Δ - Δ - Δ - Adsorption ----- Desorption

Fig. 2 - \times - \times - \times - Adsorption ----- Desorption

Fig. 3 - \circ - \circ - \circ - Adsorption ----- Desorption

Fig. 1-3. Sorption-desorption isotherms of water vapour at 35° in 1st, 2nd and 4th cycle on whole, α - and β -caseins respectively.

are the sigmoid type II isotherms of the well known classification of Brunauer, Emmett and Teller. It is seen that although hysteresis persists even upto the fourth cycle, it is not reproducible as has been reported by Benson and Richardson⁵ in the case of sorption of water and other polar vapours on egg albumin, bovine plasma albumin and gelatin. The area of the loop, in fact, keeps on decreasing at each successive cycle. The extent of sorption also keeps on falling. Thus while the amount of water sorbed by unfractionated casein at a pressure close to saturation vapour pressure (i.e., at ~ 0.95 r.v.p.) was 14 mmoles g^{-1} in the first cycle, it decreased to 10.8, 9.4 and 9.1 mmoles g^{-1} in the second, third and fourth cycles, respectively.

The area of the hysteresis loop which was equal to 103 squares, when plotted on a convenient scale, in the first cycle, decreased to 52, 31 and 23 small squares in subsequent cycles. These observations are more in line with those reported by Rao and coworkers^{6,7,9} than with those reported by Benson and Richardson⁵ on a variety of proteins. Another interesting feature of these isotherms is that the hysteresis does not persist all along the isotherm as had been observed by Berlin

et al⁸ who could not desorb the residual moisture even on pumping at 10^{-6} torr at the temperature of the isotherm (24°) for 8 days. We find that the hysteresis which commences at about 0.9 r.v.p. ends at 0.05 r.v.p. in the first cycle; the corresponding values in the fourth cycle being about 0.80 and 0.20 respectively.

The isotherms on α - and β -fractions (Fig. 2 & 3) showed similar trends. The maximum sorption values, however, are appreciably lower. The size of the loop is also relatively smaller. The reason for the higher sorption values observed in the case of unfractionated casein has already been discussed¹. The β -fraction on account of the presence of relatively smaller number of polar groups¹⁰ takes up much less water vapour than the α -fraction, and also shows the minimum area of the hysteresis loop for any given cycle.

The ratios of the area of the loop to the maximum sorption at 0.95 r.v.p. for various cycles in the case of whole casein as well as its major fractions are recorded in Table 1. It is seen that the ratio of the two quantities

TABLE 1—SIZE OF HYSTERESIS LOOP IN RELATION TO MAXIMUM SORPTION OF WATER, METHANOL AND ETHANOL ON CASEIN AND CASEIN FRACTIONS.

Description of the sample and the solvent used.	No. of cycles											
	1st			2nd			3rd			4th		
	H.A.	M.S.	H.A./M.S.	H.A.	M.S.	H.A./M.S.	H.A.	M.S.	H.A./M.S.	H.A.	M.S.	H.A./M.S.
<i>Whole casein</i>												
Water	103	14.2	7.2	52	10.6	5.0	31	9.5	3.3	23	9.1	2.5
Methanol	109	7.4	14.7	92	6.6	14.0	86	6.3	13.6	82	6.2	13.2
Ethanol	121	5.1	23.7	112	4.8	23.3	110	4.6	24.0	110	4.6	24.0
<i>α-Casein</i>												
Water	81	13.4	6.0	50	11.8	4.2	39	10.9	3.5	32	10.6	3.0
Methanol	93	7.1	13.1	88	6.9	13.0	86	6.8	13.0	86	6.8	12.8
Ethanol	101	4.9	20.6	100	4.8	21.1	99	4.8	21.6	99	4.8	21.6
<i>β-Casein</i>												
Water	64	10.8	6.0	43	8.7	5.0	28	8.0	3.5	19	7.7	2.5
Methanol	75	6.0	12.5	65	5.4	12.0	60	5.2	11.6	58	5.2	11.2
Ethanol	78	4.05	19.5	75	3.9	19.5	73	3.8	20.0	73	3.8	20.0

H.A.=Hysteresis loop area.

M.S.=Maximum sorption.

though different for different cycles, is almost constant for a given cycle in the case of all the three products. This shows that the sorption-desorption behaviour of a protein-water system varies with the number of cycles it has undergone and can be considered to be repro-

ducible only when one particular cycle is under consideration.

The isotherms for methanol and ethanol on unfractio-nated casein are shown in Fig. 4 and 5, respecti-

Fig. 4 —△—△—△— Adsorption — — — — Desorption

Fig. 4 Sorption-desorption isotherms of methanol vapour on whole casein at 35° in 1st, 2nd and 4th cycle.

Fig. 5 —△—△—△— Adsorption — — — — Desorption

Fig. 5 Sorption-desorption isotherms of ethanol vapour on whole casein at 35° in 1st, 2nd and 4th cycle.

vely. The amount of sorption is seen to be less than that of water. The values, in fact, decrease in the order: water > methanol > ethanol. The size of the hysteresis loop, however, decreases in the reverse order, viz., ethanol > methanol > water. Thus while the extent of sorption decreases, the hysteresis effect increases with increase in the molecular size of the adsorbate. It was for this reason that previous workers could not correlate the size of the hysteresis loop with the magnitude of adsorption, using various adsorbates of about the same polarity⁵. The ratio of the area of the loop to the maximum amount of vapour adsorbed is seen to increase with increase in molecular size of the adsorbate, being maximum with ethanol and minimum with water (Table 1). It is also interesting to note that this ratio which decreased nearly to one third of the initial value in the fourth cycle in the case of water, remains more or less constant now in all the four cycles. The area of the loop and the extent of sorption in the case of ethanol, in particular, remains almost the same in each cycle. In other words, the hysteresis in ethanol-casein system is almost completely reversible. Rao et al⁹ explain hysteresis and decreasing size of the loop at each succeeding cycle observed by them in the case of sorption of water by a variety of proteins including casein on the basis of the 'cavity' theory^{11,12}. According to them, the adsorbent protein is subjected to alternate swelling and shrinkage during each cycle causing gradual collapse and consequent decrease in the entrapping effect of the cavities. In support of this view they showed that with a non-solvating liquid, like carbon tetrachloride, there is a permanent and reproducible hysteresis loop. This view may not be quite convincing in the light of the reproducibility of the hysteresis even in the case of a solvating liquid, like ethanol, as reported above. Moreover, swelling of casein in water, methanol and ethanol was found to be 106, 75 and 69% respectively. If hysteresis was due only to swelling of proteins in the solvating liquids, the hysteresis effect could not have been maximum in the case of ethanol. The effect cannot be explained on the basis of hydrogen bonding either as all the three adsorbates are capable of forming hydrogen bonds and yet the magnitude of the effect is so vastly different. It appears highly likely that the molecular size of the adsorbate may also be an important factor to be taken into account while considering this phenomenon.

Benson and Richardson⁵ consider proteins to be essentially non-porous. The hysteresis effect, according to them, arises from deformation of the polypeptide

chains within the protein molecule as the polar sorbate settles into suitable positions. As an evidence, they showed that the hysteresis loop in the case of sorption on egg albumin, bovine plasma albumin and gelatin was larger in size in the case of a heavier adsorbate molecule as, for example, in the case of methanol than that in the case of water. This trend, however, was not consistent since the size of the loop in the case of the next heavier polar adsorbate molecule, namely ethanol, was less than that observed in the case of methanol. Our observations, using casein and its major fractions as adsorbents, however, show clearly that the size of the loop varies with the molecular size of the adsorbate and thus apparently support the views of Benson and Richardson. However, in view of the failure of this regularity as observed by these workers in the case of other proteins there may be a need to consider some alternative mechanism as well. The differences between the slopes of the desorption curves of water, methanol and ethanol plotted in Fig. 1, 4 and 5 are highly significant. It is seen that while the desorption of water, commencing at ~ 0.85 r. v. p., proceeds steadily thereafter with further fall in pressure, that of methanol and ethanol commencing at a slightly lower r.v.p., proceeds much more gradually. In the case of ethanol, in fact, no significant desorption is noticed until the vapour pressure of the system has been reduced to well below 0.5 r.v.p. The time required to pump out completely the various adsorbates at nearly zero r. v. p. was found to be much higher (~ 80 hr.) in the case of ethanol than that in the case of methanol (~ 48 hr.) and water (~ 6 hr.). These results indicate that the main cause of the hysteresis lies probably in the slow rate of diffusion of the adsorbate molecules from the micropores of casein, i.e., due to steric factors; the larger molecules requiring higher activation energy. Some workers⁵ regard protein as a non-porous system. But, as has been rightly pointed out⁹, an ideal plane surface is a rarity; even a non-porous adsorbent has cracks and fissures on surface. In any case, the existence of micropores of width lying between 11.7 and 14.8 Å in casein and its fractions has been indicated by the t-plots for several adsorbates². The slow rate of diffusion of the adsorbate molecules from such micropores appears to be an important factor in producing the hysteresis effect.

The values for specific surface area of the various casein adsorbents were obtained from the sorption isotherms of the various cycles by applying the B. E. T. equation. The results are given in Table 2. It is seen

TABLE 2—SPECIFIC SURFACE AREAS (M²/G) OF CASEIN AND CASEIN FRACTIONS AS OBTAINED FROM WATER, METHANOL AND ETHANOL ADSORPTION ISOTHERMS.

No. of cycles	Specific surface area								
	Water			Methanol			Ethanol		
	Whole casein	α-casein	β-casein	Whole casein	α-casein	β-casein	Whole casein	α-casein	β-casein
1st	193	190	163	188	180	149	186	175	144
2nd	161	175	140	174	173	140	184	175	142
3rd	148	167	128	171	172	138	182	175	141
4th	144	165	125	171	172	138	182	175	141

that surface area, as calculated from water isotherms, decreases appreciably at the end of the first and again at the end of the second cycle, but tends to become constant thereafter. The corresponding change in methanol area is much less while that in ethanol area is hardly significant. It appears that larger swelling in water during sorption and consequent shrinkage during desorption causes loss of a part of the surface but the situation gets stabilised after two successive cycles. Such effects are much less in the case of alcohols for obvious reasons.

The isotherms on whole (i.e., unfractionated) casein after denaturation are shown in Fig. 6. It is seen, in the first instance, that the extent of sorption is very much less than before. A similar effect has been

reported by previous workers in the case of some other proteins^{5,9}. Such observations, as they have rightly pointed out, do not indicate that denaturation causes uncoiling of the peptide chain and greater exposure of the inner polar groups because, in that case, the amount of adsorption would have increased. The fall in sorption value, at each r. v. p., appears to be due to loss of surface caused by aggregation of the particles on denaturation. The hysteresis loop for the sorption of water is now seen to be very much smaller in size than before while that for the sorption of methanol and ethanol is negligibly small (Fig. 6). Denaturation, evidently, results in loss of microporosity as well. It is also significant to note that surface area, though appreciably smaller than before, is about the same whether obtained from water, methanol or ethanol isotherms (Table 3).

Fig. 6 — Δ — Δ — Δ — Adsorption —X—X—X— Desorption

Fig. 6. Sorption-desorption isotherms of water, methanol and ethanol vapours on denatured whole casein at 35°.

TABLE 3—SPECIFIC SURFACE AREAS (M^2/G) OF DENATURED CASEIN AND CASEIN FRACTIONS AS OBTAINED FROM WATER, METHANOL AND ETHANOL ADSORPTION ISOTHERMS

Description of the sample	Specific surface areas		
	Water	Methanol	Ethanol
Whole casein	154	150	149
α -casein	161	156	154
β -casein	126	124	120

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